

Embracing Green Technology for a Sustainable Future through Talent Management

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Abstract

Green technology aims to minimize environmental impact while maximizing resource efficiency. From renewable energy sources to eco-friendly manufacturing processes, the potential of green technology to mitigate climate change and preserve our planet's natural resources is undeniable. The study paved the way for a more sustainable, equitable, and prosperous future for all through framework to balance smart, sustainable and safe work environment to improve industrial productivity. Literature survey and informal consultation and personal observations and perspective analysis is done for the study.

Energy Independence: Homes equipped with energy generation and storage capabilities will not only reduce reliance on the grid but also contribute to a more sustainable energy ecosystem, with potential for selling excess energy back to industries.

Technological Disruption: Drawing parallels to past industry upheavals like Kodak's demise, the rapid advancement of technologies such as artificial intelligence, autonomous vehicles, and renewable energy sources foretell a future where adaptation and innovation are paramount.

Educational Path: The future educational path will be shown for talent management. The study has significantly addressed the issues of agriculture in Nepal for promoting industry in Nepal. The dynamics moves towards the imminent rise of electric cars and the accompanying shift in repair and maintenance paradigms signify a pivotal moment in automotive history. Embracing these changes will not only revolutionize transportation but also pave the way for a more sustainable, efficient, and technologically advanced future. By fostering a culture of continuous learning, creativity, and collaboration, organizations can attract, develop, and retain top talent in the green technology sector. Investing in training programs, mentorship initiatives, and diversity and inclusion efforts can help cultivate a diverse pool of talent equipped to tackle the complex challenges of sustainability and environmental stewardship.

As we embark on this journey towards a greener, more sustainable tomorrow, it is essential that we embrace the transformative potential of green technology and nurture the talent that will drive this revolution forward. By doing so, we can create a future where environmental preservation, economic growth, and societal well-being is not mutually exclusive, but rather, inextricably linked.

Keywords: *Dynamic, Learning, Digital, Sustainable, Balance, safe, productive*